

LISTENING SKILLS

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Annotation: in this article, you can read about types of listening. How to develop students' ability to listen during the lessons. There are several statements on how to achieve good results in the teaching process.

Keywords: Listening skills, intensive listening, extensive listening, TPR, TED talks, podcasts.

Intensive listening is a type of listening practice which directs the attention of language learners to their language knowledge and requires them to note contrasts of language form, viz. sound, structure, and lexical choice, in the process of comprehension and interpretation of the aural input.[1] Identifying details, figures, and place names in addition to people, phrases, language, and information are examples of targeted listening. One way to conceptualise intensive listening is to pay extra attention to distinctive details. This can assist in teaching how to apply grammatical rules and structures to specific speech situations. For novices who don't know enough about the target language, it is helpful. As an illustration, a teacher can assign the verb practice exercise "Put the events in order." Using the task physical response (TPR) method, an instructor states many actions while modelling them. Consider greeting and saying hello to your neighbour (a teacher shaking hands with a few students), giving your teddy bear a hug (a teacher modelling the act of giving a hug), and feeding your teddy bear (a teacher giving the teddy something to eat). After determining that the students have understood the actions, the teacher repeats them and plays the audio. Next, give them visual handouts and ask them to mark the appropriate occurrence by listening to the audio. Extended listening: the primary goal of this kind of instruction is to provide students a comprehensive comprehension of

the listening task. Students that listen extensively are able to understand lengthy audio talks and assess their significance. For advanced pupils, thorough listening might be helpful because it uses high-level vocabulary. Podcasts, TED speeches, and political debates, for instance, are appropriate for prolonged listening. There are numerous ways to practise thorough listening, such paying attention to a native speaker or attending a lecture. Students' academic vocabulary can be developed through listening to scientific lectures. A teacher should assign reading materials based on the assigned listening task, provide students with detailed instructions on how to complete it, and then play a lecture on the radio. Four or five questions, depending on the assignment, may be asked. hearing for the gist: this kind of hearing entails paying attention to comprehend the overall point of the listening task. A teacher can improve the learners' ability to listen to comprehend the whole meaning. However, it is essential to pay attention to the learners' level of knowledge. Beginners can have difficulties in listening for gist. The reason is the shortage of advanced vocabulary. To overcome this problem, a teacher should explain the functions of parts of speech, the pronunciation of the words and phrases, and the spelling. Listening for detail: to improve students' capacity to understand particular information in the listening assignments, a teacher should use this strategy. It can be helpful for analysing numbers, names of places or people, and the amount of something from the task. For example, a teacher can use it to explain tenses, parts of speech or principles of Grammar. Materials for use in listening activities include audiobooks, music, TED talks, movies and podcast, which are known as listening materials. A teacher may lead a debate or discussion on politicians that is suitable for advanced students. It helps recognise sophisticated and academic language. They have a smooth and organised speech pattern. Pupils can mimic the way that words and phrasal verbs are used in speech. Additionally, through their speeches, they pick up complex sentence structures.[2]Listening is assuming greater and greater importance in foreign language classrooms. There are several reasons for this growth in popularity. By emphasizing the role of comprehensible input, second language acquisition research has given a major boost to listening. [3]To teach listening skills

efficiently, teachers should introduce key scientific terms and concepts that students may encounter in the article and provide definitions and examples to ensure understanding; and engage students in a discussion or activity related to the topic of the scientific article. This helps activate their prior knowledge and creates a context for better comprehension; and clearly define the purpose of the listening activity; give students an overview of the scientific article. Highlight the main ideas, subheadings, and any visual aids such as graphs or diagrams. This helps students anticipate the content and structure of the article; pre-listening Activities: conduct activities that prepare students for listening. These can include brainstorming related ideas, predicting content based on the title, or discussing questions related to the topic; provide students with a copy of the scientific article or a transcript of the audio recording; encourage them to actively listen for specific information or main ideas. They can take notes, underline key points, or summarize sections as they listen; post-listening Activities: Engage students in activities that reinforce comprehension and critical thinking. These can include discussions, debates, comprehension questions, summarizing the article, or analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of the research presented; assign tasks that extend learning beyond the listening activity. This can include writing a summary of the article, conducting further research on the topic, or presenting a critique of the research methodology; offer constructive feedback on students' listening skills, language use, and comprehension. Individual feedback helps students identify areas for improvement and encourages their progress; incorporate regular listening activities into your curriculum to provide ongoing practice and reinforcement of listening skills. Use a variety of scientific articles to expose students to different topics, styles, and levels of complexity.

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